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Linking Blue Carbon hopes and realities to research, valuation and governance efforts in the island states of the South West Indian Ocean

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ABSTRACT

Island states in the South West Indian Ocean (SWIO), including Mauritius, Madagascar and Seychelles, hold substantial but underrecognized blue carbon potential across both coastal and deep-sea waters. While national efforts have begun to quantify and protect static blue carbon solutions such as mangroves and seagrasses, the region's deeper waters, where over 90%

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of Mauritian, Malagasy and Seychelles waters lie below 200 m, remain underrepresented in blue carbon research, accounting, valuation and governance frameworks. This publication reviews the current status of blue carbon science, finance, and policy in Mauritius, Madagascar and Seychelles, and highlights the emerging importance of mobile blue carbon associated with marine fauna such as whales and deep-sea fishes, crustaceans, and squids (collectively referred to as “micronekton”). This document identifies key scientific, financial, and governance challenges that constrain the integration of blue carbon into climate policy and carbon markets, including data gaps, methodological limitations, certification barriers, fragmented expertise and institutional frameworks.

Addressing these challenges will require the development and strengthening of environmental law and regulatory frameworks that recognize blue carbon as part of national marine natural capital within maritime jurisdictions, including exclusive economic zones, joint management areas (JMA), and adjacent areas beyond national jurisdiction. In jointly managed regions, such as the Mauritius-Seychelles JMA, blue carbon governance can provide an additional legal and cooperative dimension to existing bilateral agreements, supporting shared management, valuation, and protection of transboundary carbon services.

Drawing on regional case studies and international guidance, this document reflects the perspectives of SWIO partners and proposes a phased implementation roadmap, spanning:

(1) strengthening scientific baselines through data compilation, new field observations, and improving laboratory or modelling research works, (2) integrating blue carbon into national policy frameworks, (3) implementing pilot projects, (4) developing measurement, verification and reporting systems, (5) policy mainstreaming and legislative amendments, (6) exploring innovative long-term finance mechanisms, (7) establishing regional knowledge hubs and governance frameworks, (8) strengthening ecosystem protection and conservation, (9) ensuring sustainable livelihoods and economic benefits for local communities, and (10) positioning the SWIO blue carbon solutions within global climate diplomacy.

The roadmap emphasizes the need to strengthen regional capacity by supporting long-term career pathways for early- and mid-career researchers, improved access to oceanographic infrastructure and analytical tools, cross-sectorial institutional coordination and capacity sharing, and joint governance frameworks. Recognizing and valuing both coastal and deep-sea blue carbon would enable SWIO island states to better account for the climate services provided by their ocean territories, mobilize climate finance, and align conservation, climate mitigation, and sustainable development objectives. The SWIO region is well positioned to become a global leader in integrated blue carbon solutions if scientific, financial and policy actions advance in concert.

1. KEYWORDS

Blue Carbon, Ocean valuation, Small island developing states, marine heritage, Marine living resources, Western Indian Ocean, Waters under jurisdiction, Republic of Seychelles, Republic of Mauritius, Republic of Madagascar, Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction

2. GLOSSARY, UNITS & ABBREVIATIONS

Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ): Commonly called the high seas, these areas of the ocean are for which no one nation has sole responsibility for management.

Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement: The BBNJ Agreement, adopted under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), addresses the conservation and sustainable use of marine biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction.

Blue Bond: A debt instrument to raise funds for marine and ocean-based projects that have long-term sustainability objectives and benefits.

Blue Carbon: All forms of marine, intertidal, and estuarine carbon processes that capture, store, and sequester carbon.

Blue Economy strategies: National or regional policy frameworks that promote sustainable use of ocean and coastal resources for economic development, livelihoods, and ecosystem health.

Blue Insurance: Insurance products created to reduce risks to marine ecosystems and to promote sustainable practices.

Blue Loan: Loans to support positive impacts on the ocean and water systems, often with terms linked to conservation results.

Conference of the Parties (COP): The supreme decision-making

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body of the Convention. All States that are Parties to the Convention are represented at the COP, at which they review the implementation of the Convention and any other legal instruments that the COP adopts and take decisions necessary to promote the effective implementation of the Convention, including institutional and administrative arrangements.

Debt-for-nature swap: Debt relief for environmental action that may finance conservation and restoration efforts.

Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ): A maritime area (waters) over which a coastal state exercises sovereign and economic rights regarding the exploitation and use of natural (both living and non-living) resources. It is known as waters under jurisdiction of the coastal state.

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): An intergovernmental body of the United Nations that provides policymakers with regular scientific assessments on climate change, its implications, and potential future risks, as well as to put forward adaptation and mitigation options.

a Joint Managed Area (JMA): a legal status for cases of a common Extended Continental Shelf jointly owned and managed by two States.

Measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV): The collection of data and information at a national (or subnational) level, and performance of the necessary calculations for estimating emission reductions or enhancement of carbon stocks and associated uncertainties against a reference level.

National Adaptation Plans (NAPs): National processes and plans to identify and address medium- and long-term climate adaptation priorities.

Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs): Commitments that countries make to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions as part of climate change mitigation. Submissions are made to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) under the Paris Agreement.

Small island developing states (SIDS): A distinct group of States and Associate Members of the United Nations regional commissions that face unique social, economic, and environmental vulnerabilities. SIDS are recognized as a special case both for their environment and development at the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, and are thus supported by various UN Programme of Action. SIDS are often characterised by a reversed ratio between their land-size and maritime territory.

United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS): UNCLOS is widely recognized as the general legal framework within which all activities conducted in the oceans and seas must take place.

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC): International environmental treaty to combat «dangerous human interference with the climate system», in part by stabilizing greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere.

Verified Carbon Standard (VCS): It is the world's most widely used programme to date to purchase carbon offsets. VCS

verifies projects that result in emissions reductions. Projects follow rigorous assessment criteria to be certified. Once projects are certified, they are issued tradeable greenhouse gas credits called Verified Carbon Units (VCUs) that can be sold on the open market and bought by companies seeking to offset their own emissions.

3. HOW DO WE DEFINE BLUE CARBON?

Fossil carbon dioxide emissions per capita increased by 6.3% in Mauritius and 1.8% in Madagascar, while Seychelles recorded a slight decrease of 0.2% in 2022 (Worldometer, 2025). In an effort to reduce these carbon dioxide emissions, there are increasing interests to investigate the blue carbon stock potential. As part of their marine heritage, island states of the SWIO hold significant, yet underrecognized, potential for carbon sequestration and storage, both in coastal ecosystems (mangroves and seagrasses) and in their deeper waters. To fully harness both this ecological and economic potential, it is essential to integrate scientific research with robust valuation approaches and governance reforms. Such integration will allow Mauritius, Madagascar, and Seychelles to capture the full spectrum of blue carbon services of their waters and to engage more effectively with global climate finance mechanisms. Blue carbon has the potential to help countries pursue the goals of the Paris Agreement by providing a tractable mechanism of carbon storage and sequestration (Brodeur, 2022). However, the first step is to define blue carbon.

Blue carbon does not yet benefit from a fully consolidated definition under the UNFCCC. Definitions and valuation methods remain fragmented, limiting access to global carbon finance and integration into national accounting. There are recent incentives to broaden the blue carbon definition to encompass all forms of marine, intertidal, and estuarine carbon processes (Sheehy et al., 2024).

“Blue carbon is the carbon captured, stored, and the rate at which it is buried, i.e., sequestered by marine organisms.”

Nature-based blue carbon solutions that are established (for e.g., mangroves, salt marshes, and seagrass meadows) meet the minimum standards of scientific understanding and implementation potential by offering scientifically verifiable levels of carbon abatement and are amenable to funding through carbon markets (Claes et al., 2022). Established solutions are hereafter referred to as “static” blue carbon solutions. Emerging solutions (e.g., kelp forests, bottom-trawled sediments, seaweed farms) are those that hold carbon dioxide abatement potential but for which further research is required to align with current funding frameworks. Nascent solutions with regards to predators, mesopelagic fauna, and whales which are highly migratory or very mobile are hereafter collectively referred to as “mobile blue carbon solutions”. They are potentially the largest and the more ambitious solutions ultimately requiring the protection of marine faunal populations (Fig. 1).

4. STATUS OF BLUE CARBON ACCOUNTING

Blue carbon valuation involves a two-step process to measure the volume of carbon dioxide sequestered and to multiply it

Fig. 1 Summary of blue carbon solutions, ranked according to their scientific and economic maturity as established, emerging, and nascent

[Credits: Claes, J., Hopman, D., Jaeger, G., Rogers, M., 2022. Blue carbon: The potential of coastal and oceanic climate action. McKinsey & Company. Hong Kong, China]

by the price of one ton of carbon on voluntary or regulated markets. The price of carbon varies according to countries and markets and is subject to an increase in the future (Berzaghi et al., 2025). The carbon market is divided into a voluntary market which is open and flexible and a regulated market which is more remunerative but less accessible (for example the European Union market has stopped accepting foreign credits since 2020).

4.1. Static Blue carbon solutions

Island states in the SWIO are currently investigating their static blue carbon solutions, i.e., those solutions that are physically embedded in substrata.

4.1.1 Processes underway in Mauritius

Mauritius aims to strengthen its national leadership in blue carbon by pursuing a comprehensive set of objectives. These include identifying, mapping, and assessing blue carbon ecosystems (BCEs) across its entire EEZ; quantifying carbon stocks and sequestration potential in under-explored offshore and remote island regions; integrating blue carbon data into national climate policies and commitments, such as the NDCs and the Blue Economy Strategy; and advancing regional collaboration and scientific leadership in blue carbon research and climate resilience. To support this ambition, Mauritius has committed to expanding its national inventory of BCEs across the full maritime zone, including the shallow Saya de Malha and Nazareth Banks, as well as the outer islands of Agalega, Rodrigues, St. Brandon, and the Chagos archipelago.

The first national blue carbon project, focused on seagrass distribution, carbon storage assessment (Fig. 2), and long-term monitoring (Ramah et al., 2026), catalysed a significant legislative shift: the prohibition of any damage to mangroves, seagrasses, or corals in the Republic Of Mauritius Fisheries Act 2023. As an output of the project, in June 2024, the Government established the National Blue Carbon Task Force (NBCTF) to convene local practitioners, strengthen capacity, and guide evidence-based decision-making on blue carbon. The NBCTF is mandated to develop standardised methodologies and protocols, provide technical and policy recommendations, explore implementation pathways, support policy reform, and identify opportunities for climate finance and adaptation aligned with national, regional, and international frameworks. Its structure comprises a main committee supported by two specialised working groups, one scientific and one focused on finance and markets, which meet periodically to advance work on data compilation, the national action plan, the national inventory of blue carbon solutions, and emerging finance and market mechanisms.

Under this task force, new collaborative projects are being implemented, notably the ecosystem services of seagrass and mangroves, and carbon stock assessment in mangroves. Building on this coordinated approach, Mauritius now seeks to integrate all components of blue finance, including blue impact investing, blue bonds, blue insurance, blue loans, and debt-for-nature swaps, under a unified and strategically aligned Mauritian Blue Economy.

Fig. 2: Blue carbon project on seagrass distribution and carbon storage assessment in Mauritius by the Ministry of Agro-Industry, Food Security, Blue Economy & Fisheries, in collaboration with the University of Mauritius

[Credits: Ramah, S., Vanderklift, M.A., Wilson, M.S., 2026. Organic and inorganic carbon stocks in seagrass sediments of Mauritius. *Sci. Total Environ.* 1014, 181396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2026.181396>].

4.1.2 Processes underway in Madagascar

Large island states, unlike SIDS, tend to primarily direct efforts towards Land-Estuarines-Coastline measures of carbon sequestration. Since mangroves may provide an extended terrestrial territory, the evaluation of the sequestration potential of mangroves are favoured on political agendas. Shifting attention to maritime areas is a challenge in technical, scientific, and legislative prioritisation.

Hosting approximately 2% of the world's mangroves, Madagascar has a significant blue carbon sequestration potential. The country launched its first blue carbon project in 2019, to conserve and reforest over 1,200 hectares of mangroves through community-based initiatives to avoid the emission of over 1,300 tons of carbon dioxide annually and to ensure long-term sustainability and equitable benefit-sharing. Registered with the Vivo Plan Standard, the aim of the project is to provide a steady income through the sale of carbon credits to support local conservation efforts over the next twenty years, to help finance community development, including the construction of vital infrastructure, and to support healthcare and education. This blue carbon credit project demonstrates that it is possible to reconcile ecosystem conservation, climate change mitigation, and the economic development of local communities. The aim is to convert the ecological value of mangroves into tangible revenues for the populations that depend on them.

4.1.3 Processes underway in Seychelles

Blue carbon as a central pillar

The Seychelles Government has positioned blue carbon as a central pillar of its economy and policy. Seychelles is a pioneer in innovative blue economy financing. In 2018, it launched the world's first sovereign blue bond, a globally significant initiative that raised US\$15 million to strengthen sustainable marine fisheries through public, private, governmental, and

philanthropic organisations. It also converted US\$21.6 million of national debt via the world's first Blue Economy debt-for-nature swap to support the expansion and management of marine protected areas (MPAs) through the Seychelles' Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT) (The Commonwealth, 2025). The bond, underpinned by the Seychelles Blue Economy Strategic Policy Framework and Roadmap, channels funds through SeyCCAT and the Development Bank of Seychelles (DBS), providing a blended finance mechanism that delivers both grants and concessional loans for sustainable-use MPAs, improved fisheries governance, and activities that contribute directly to blue carbon conservation.

Seychelles is committed to protecting at least 50% of its seagrass and mangrove ecosystems by 2025, and 100% by 2030, in its 2021 NDC presented at the Glasgow COP in 2021 (Rowlands et al., 2024). Towards these targets, Seychelles mapped the full extent of the blue carbon seagrass and mangrove ecosystems within its EEZ and measured their carbon stock values under the Seychelles Seagrass Mapping and Carbon Assessment Project. Approximately 160,000 hectares of seagrass and 2,195 hectares of mangrove were mapped across Seychelles' EEZ (Fig. 3) which has been estimated to store 19.6 million tons of organic carbon (equivalent of 71.7 million tons of carbon dioxide) with an overall sequestration rate of 524 kt CO₂e per year (Rowlands et al., 2024).

In particular, Seychelles southern islands which are part of the Marine Spatial Plan Zone 1 (High biodiversity protection zone), recorded the highest estimates of total carbon stocks arising from important seagrass beds and mangrove mudflats (Fig. 4). A total of 99.5% of seagrass habitats are found within designated protected zones. The Marine Spatial Plan, approved by the Seychelles Cabinet, designates 30% (15% High Biodiversity Protection Zone and 15% Medium Biodiversity Protection and Sustainable Use Zone) of the EEZ for biodiversity protection while supporting the blue economy and climate adaptation objectives (SMSPI, 2025). Within this national framework of

Fig. 3: Seagrass maps for Seychelles Southern islands including:
 A) Providence Bank; B) Farquhar;
 C) Cosmoledo; D) Astove;
 E) Aldabra; and F) Assumption.

[Credits: Rowlands GP, Antat S, Baez SK, Cupidon A, Faure A, Harlay J, Lee CB, Martin LEC, Masque P, Morgan M, Mortimer JA, Traganos D, (2024). The Seychelles Seagrass Mapping and Carbon Assessment. A report to be submitted to the Government of Seychelles, Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE)].

Fig. 4: Map of the Republic of Seychelles and its Marine Spatial Plan
 [Credits: Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan Initiative (SMSPi). (2025). Seychelles Cabinet approves Marine Spatial Plan].

blue-carbon conservation and spatial protection, the Aldabra Atoll, recognized as a UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) marine World Heritage Site, represents one of Seychelles' most emblematic and high-value coastal blue-carbon ecosystems.

Building on these scientific baselines, Seychelles has developed a Blue Carbon Roadmap that sets a long-term, evidence-based pathway to protect, restore, and sustainably manage BCEs, translating ecosystem mapping and carbon-stock assessments into a coordinated national programme for climate mitigation, adaptation, and policy integration. Central to the roadmap is a protection first approach, whereby blue carbon solutions are safeguarded through policies, regulations, licenses, or permitting, only allowing activities that are consistent with avoiding and minimising identifiable impacts to seagrass habitats and/or sediments. In Seychelles, blue carbon solutions such as seagrass and mangroves are both recognized by the IPCC. The Seychelles Seagrass Mapping and Carbon Assessment Project demonstrated how protecting blue carbon solutions may help in climate action. The resulting methodology from this project may be adapted and scaled to the Saya de Malha Bank, which is jointly managed by Mauritius and Seychelles (JMA).

∫ Seychelles 2024 Blue Carbon Policy

Building on these foundational research and mapping achievements, Seychelles has taken a significant step toward translating scientific knowledge into governance action through the development of a national Blue Carbon Policy, finalised in October 2024. Drafted under the auspices of the Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE), with contributions from multi-stakeholder consultations, the policy represents the first comprehensive national framework in the SWIO to operationalise blue carbon conservation, restoration, and potential monetisation within a single, binding instrument.

The policy establishes a clear hierarchy of priorities. Its primary commitment is to ensure that 100% of Seychelles' BCEs including; mangroves and seagrass meadows are protected by 2030, consistent with the country's 2021 NDC obligations. Crucially, the policy positions blue carbon sequestration as a contribution to Seychelles' own NDC targets first, with any surplus carbon stocks then eligible for entry into voluntary or compliance carbon markets. This principle is an important governance signal for the region, ensuring that blue carbon assets are not prematurely commodified at the expense of national climate commitments.

The policy articulates four core objectives: (i) climate mitigation through leveraging BCEs as carbon sinks; (ii) ecosystem protection and conservation of mangroves and seagrass meadows; (iii) coastal protection and climate adaptation; and (iv) sustainable livelihoods and economic benefits for coastal communities. These objectives are tightly aligned with sustainable development goals (SDGs) 13 (Climate Action), 14 (Life Below Water), and 15 (Life on Land), as well as with Seychelles' broader Blue Economy Strategy.

On the legal and institutional front, the policy proposes a suite of targeted legislative amendments to entrench blue carbon protection in national law. The Environmental Protection Act

(2016), Fisheries Act (2014), Forest Reserves Act (1976), and Physical Planning Act (2021) are all identified for revision to include explicit provisions for blue carbon habitats. These amendments would, for the first time, give mangroves and seagrass meadows specific statutory recognition, closing a governance gap noted in the existing legal framework. The policy also identifies the Saya de Malha Bank jointly managed under a Mauritius-Seychelles JMA as requiring a dedicated bilateral Memorandum of Understanding or treaty to address blue carbon governance beyond national jurisdiction, a matter of direct relevance to the broader SWIO governance agenda discussed in this document.

Institutionally, the policy mandates the establishment of an Inter-Ministerial Working Group (chaired by the MACCE) to oversee cross-sectoral implementation, and a National Blue Carbon Taskforce comprising government, private sector, civil society, and research representatives. These structures mirror the institutional architecture being developed in Mauritius, suggesting an emerging regional model for blue carbon governance coordination. Importantly, the policy also provides for the formalisation of district-level community associations and mandates compulsory public participation processes for blue carbon projects, recognising that community engagement is not ancillary but central to achieving durable conservation outcomes.

The policy's MRV framework is designed to align with international carbon market standards while remaining nationally governed. Carbon stock reports are to be submitted annually, and an independent verification body is to be established and accredited under internationally recognised protocols. Third-party verification, additionality, permanence, and leakage prevention are all stipulated as requirements for blue carbon credit certification, consistent with the VCS, Gold Standard, and Plan Vivo frameworks. The policy's approach to carbon credit integration is deliberately cautious: private participation in carbon markets must be certified, regulated, and recorded by the Seychelles government, and the overall carbon market strategy will be coordinated under a broader national carbon strategy being developed by the Ministry of Finance.

A detailed implementation roadmap with 21 actions spanning 2025-2030 accompanies the policy. Key near-term milestones include: ratification by Cabinet (February 2025); establishment of the Inter-Ministerial Working Group (December 2025); development of a national carbon market framework and registry (December 2025); establishment of an independent verification body and an early warning system for illegal degradation (June 2026); and the mapping of BCEs (particularly mangrove ecosystems in the short term) with determination of carbon sequestration rates (December 2026). The expansion of protected areas to cover 100% of BCEs is targeted for completion by June 2030.

Taken together, the Seychelles Blue Carbon Policy represents a significant and replicable governance innovation for the SWIO. It demonstrates how a SIDS can systematically link scientific baselines, legal reform, institutional coordination, community engagement, and market mechanisms into a

Fig. 5: Nascent blue carbon solutions

[Credits: Lutz SJ, Glavan J, Rubilla A, 2019. Assessment of Oceanic Blue carbon in the UAE: Policy Options. AGEDI, Abu Dhabi, UAE, GRID-Arendal, Arendal, Norway, and Blue Climate Solutions, Washington, DC, USA. 48 pp].

coherent national framework. Several of its design featuring the NDC-first sequencing, the phased roadmap, the inter-ministerial governance model, the mandatory community participation processes, and the bilateral dimension with Mauritius on the Saya de Malha Bank, offer direct lessons for Madagascar and Mauritius as they advance their own blue carbon governance frameworks. As the region moves toward the kind of coordinated blue carbon hub envisaged in Phase 3 of the roadmap set out in Section 6, Seychelles’ policy architecture provides a strong regional anchor from which to build.

4.2. Promises of mobile blue carbon solutions

We refer as “mobile blue carbon” taxa that contribute to carbon transport and sequestration but are not stationary, either because they drift with ocean currents (e.g., phytoplankton) or because they are capable of actively swimming, such as megafauna (e.g., whales), zooplankton and deep-sea fishes, squids, and crustaceans, collectively known as “micronekton” (Fig. 5).

After significant promotion of coastal blue carbon, the International Union for Conservation of Nature issued a call for action in 2014 to expand the blue-carbon agenda from coastal zones to the wider ocean (Jiao et al., 2018). The ocean has sequestered more than 25% of excess anthropogenic carbon dioxide since the mid-1990s (Watson et al., 2020), with the deep sea (below 200 m depth) being the largest carbon sink on Earth (Hilmi et al., 2023). Deep-sea blue carbon involves carbon fluxes and storage such as the carbon transferred from the atmosphere by inorganic and organic carbon pumps to deeper waters,

carbon sequestered in the bodies of deep-sea organisms (i.e., the biological carbon pump - BCP) and in the carcasses of sinked dead animals, and carbon buried within sediments or captured in carbonate rocks (Hilmi et al., 2023). Processes within the BCP contribute to climate regulation by transporting carbon fixed at the ocean surface to depth, where it can remain sequestered for decades to centuries (Boyd et al., 2019). In the SWIO, where over 90% of Mauritian, Malagasy and Seychelles waters lie below 200 m, the biomass and carbon transport capacity of deep-sea organisms are substantial. Recent estimates suggest that carbon sequestration associated with the BCP may represent ~5% of Madagascar’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP), ~10% of Mauritius’ GDP, and over 100% of Seychelles’ GDP using conservative transport capacity from current models, and when valued at carbon market prices of US\$90 tCO₂-1. The present value of carbon sequestration by the BCP in the EEZ of these countries could reach tens to hundreds of billions of USD by 2050, representing a major natural capital asset (Fig. 6).

Whales are increasingly recognised as ecologically significant global commons and emerging “mobile blue carbon” actors, contributing to climate regulation through their role in carbon capture, biological productivity, and long-term carbon storage within marine ecosystems. At its 66th (2016) and 67th (2018) meetings, the International Whaling Commission (IWC) formally recognised whales’ contribution to ocean carbon cycling and climate regulation. Through the Resolution on Advancing the Commission’s Work on the Role of Cetaceans in Ecosystem Functioning and the Florianópolis Declaration, member states adopted resolutions to encourage countries to integrate the ecological and climate-related value of cetaceans

Fig. 6:
 (a) Carbon sequestration potential (Gigatons of carbon dioxide per year) of the biological carbon pump in the exclusive economic zones of Mauritius, Madagascar, and Seychelles.
 (b) The sum of present value (future cash flow) of carbon services of EEZs from present until 2030/2050 (at a price of US\$90 tCO₂-1 as suggested by the IPCC)

into biodiversity, environmental, and climate policy processes. Member states also tasked the IWC’s Scientific Committee with advancing research on the links between whale conservation, ecosystem functioning, and carbon dynamics. Together, these resolutions marked a shift in the IWC’s mandate toward a broader ecosystem-based and climate-aware approach to cetacean conservation, while stopping short of formal carbon accounting or inclusion in national climate commitments. Chami et al. (2019) proposed a framework to assess the financial value of the ecological services around carbon sinks provided by whales, using available carbon trading prices as benchmarks. The authors suggest creating financial mechanisms following the United Nations REDD program that provides incentives to countries to preserve their natural carbon assets as a means of keeping carbon dioxide out of the atmosphere. Incentives in the form of subsidies or other compensation could help those who incur costs as a result of whale protection (e.g., shipping companies could be compensated for the cost of altered shipping routes to reduce collision risks). Support for mitigation measures could come from the Global Environment Facility (<https://www.thegef.org/>), which typically supports countries to meet international environmental agreements.

Mobile blue carbon solutions are increasingly being appraised for their carbon storage potential, but they are not presently framed in the blue carbon context (Cavan et al., 2024). The application of ecosystem services to mobile blue carbon would allow their economic valuation, pay for the services rendered, ecological compensation, and comprehensive management of the deep ocean falling under EEZs or JMAs. A viable market for ocean carbon would allow indebted states to reduce their debt by obtaining payments for maintaining or enhancing this carbon reduction service. Valuing mobile blue solutions would give

Mauritius, Madagascar, and Seychelles a better understanding of the climate services their deep waters provide, hence supporting better-informed management decisions and investments. Accurately quantifying mobile blue carbon solutions and bringing this ecosystem service to blue carbon accounting is, therefore, not only a scientific gap to fill, but also an opportunity to recognize and sustain a major natural asset for the region.

5. KNOWN CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

5.1. Scientific challenges and potential solutions

While blue carbon solutions may help island states in the SWIO to reach net-zero emissions, significant scientific, economic, and policy hurdles exist in blue carbon assessment and valuation. The scientific hurdles include the quantification of carbon captured using standardised protocols, lack of data time series, and lack of representative ecosystem modelling of mobile blue carbon transport and sequestration pathways (Annasawmy et al., 2026). To achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement, it is important to promote research to generate data, accurately estimate the biomass of deep-sea organisms as they can act as a carbon repository over long residence times (NASEM, 2022), and to better parametrize models of carbon transport for quantification of uncertainties and comprehensive estimations (Annasawmy et al., 2026). Ecosystem services frameworks that explicitly link human well-being to environmental processes provide a useful entry point for capacity sharing, as they allow scientists, policymakers, and finance actors to jointly identify and quantify provisioning, regulating (including climate regulation and carbon sequestration), and cultural services provided by marine and deep-sea ecosystems (Hilmi et al., 2023). Methodological frameworks have been established to

provide evidence of where and when marine carbon in deep-sea ecosystems can provide regulating services by contributing to climate mitigation (Graves et al., 2022). Applying these frameworks would require strengthened regional expertise in ocean biogeochemistry, carbon flux modelling, valuation methods, and MRV system design.

5.2. Financial challenges and potential solutions

A limited number of projects have qualified for carbon markets to date, since blue carbon projects may appear high risk, subscale, and expensive (Claes et al., 2022; Bach et al., 2025). Many blue carbon projects do not currently meet the standard of scientific certainty about the impacts of abatement actions since there are uncertainties about the proportion of carbon accumulated and cycled by marine fauna and the influence of sediments on the sequestration rate. These blue carbon projects face significant barriers to accessing voluntary carbon markets because they struggle to meet the Core Carbon Principles that guide voluntary carbon market funding (Claes et al., 2022). Financial challenges in the region are further compounded by limited fiscal space, high transaction costs associated with project certification, and reliance on external technical expertise, which can slow project development and reduce national ownership. Persistent financial challenge across the SWIO is the difficulty of sustaining momentum once pilot or donor-funded projects conclude. Scaling up beyond the project cycle requires predictable long-term financing streams that support maintenance, monitoring, and adaptive management of restored ecosystems.

Alternative methods of carbon accounting are emerging to accommodate impermanent blue carbon solutions to derive carbon credits (e.g., Balmford et al., 2023). Valuing deep

ecosystem services is challenging because these benefits operate as non-fungible assets since they are unique environmental assets that cannot be easily exchanged in the marketplace. Emerging blockchain-based tokenization frameworks offer a potential pathway for addressing this non-fungibility by assigning digital tokens to specific deep-sea environmental services (Hilmi et al., 2023). Similar approaches already exist, for example, Orb issuing verified carbon credits in the form of non-fungible tokens to allow for the validation, measurement, and verification of carbon afforestation projects (www.orb.green). The conceptual architecture could, in principle, be adapted to the deep-sea blue carbon solutions (Hilmi et al., 2023). The scale of blue carbon abatement offered by marine fauna is too large to be ignored. Concerted action between scientists, modellers, economists, policy-makers, stakeholders and industry is required to build momentum through demand signals and investments in technology and science.

While blue carbon is rapidly becoming an important solution to offset greenhouse gas emissions, collectives such as the Blue Carbon Buyers Alliance are rising to profile high-quality blue carbon projects, mobilizing additional funding (such as philanthropic and public finance) for capacity building and science needed to scale the supply of high-quality blue carbon credits to the market. Governmental actions are critical in scaling participation and funding to support blue carbon projects, and by including blue carbon solutions in their NDCs under the Paris Agreement. Since funds from the World Bank arising through blue carbon go to the governments and do not necessarily translate to local communities, States should closely engage with local peoples and small-scale food-producing communities, respecting access and tenure rights.

Table 1. Phase 1 : Baseline, Assessment & Enabling Environment (Years 1-3).

BCEs stands for Blue Carbon Ecosystems, GCF for Green Climate Fund, GEF for Global Environment Facility, IOC for Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission, IUCN for International Union for Conservation of Nature, UNEP for UN Environment Programme, UNDP for the United Nations Development Programme, and WIOMSA for the Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association.

Action Area	Specific Actions	Lead / Supporting Institutions	Timeframe	Finance Options	Key References
1. Data Collection & Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compile existing data - Conduct field surveys for biomass & sediment carbon - Improve laboratory or modelling research works - Prioritise offshore banks & outer islands 	Environment ministries; research institutes; universities; regional bodies (WIOMSA, IOC)	1-3 years	GCF readiness; GEF; national budgets; bilateral donors	IPCC Wetlands Supplement; Ocean Panel Blue Carbon Handbook; Abu Dhabi Global Environmental Data Initiative Policy Report; Annasawmy et al. (2026)
2. National Policy Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include BCEs in NDCs, NAPs, Blue Economy strategies - Review legal frameworks for BCE protection 	Climate ministries; Attorney General's office; Blue Economy units	1-2 years	NDC implementation funds; UNDP; UNEP	IUCN National Blue Carbon Guidance
3. Institutional Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish/strengthen national task forces - Create cross-sector working groups (science & finance) - Develop national workplans 	National task forces; inter-ministerial committees	1-2 years	Technical assistance; regional cooperation grants	

Table 2. Phase 2 : Pilots, MRV Systems & Policy Mainstreaming (Years 2-6).

DRR stands for Disaster Risk Reduction, FAO for the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, GEF for Global Environment Facility, MPA for Marine Protected Area, MSP for marine spatial planning, NGOs for Non-Governmental Organisations, and UNEP for UN Environment Programme.

Action Area	Specific Actions	Lead / Supporting Institutions	Timeframe	Finance Options	Key References
4. Pilot Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement mangrove & seagrass pilots - Test restoration & conservation models for seagrass - For mobile blue carbon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prioritize science-first pilots before market claims - Implement mobile blue carbon pilot assessments (first-order audits) within EEZs, using existing datasets and targeted new observations (e.g., active acoustics, fisheries-independent surveys) - Monitor all forms of carbon, biodiversity & socio-economic outcomes 	Research institutes; NGOs; community groups; MPAs	2–5 years	Blue carbon pilots; GEF; philanthropy; blended finance	Ramah et al. (2026); Annasawmy et al. (2026); peer-reviewed BCE studies; Abu Dhabi Global Environmental Data Initiative Policy Report ;
5. National MRV Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop national MRV frameworks - Standardise sampling protocols - Integrate BCEs into national GHG inventories Mobile blue carbon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardize data sampling and processing protocols for biomass and carbon transport and sequestration evaluations. - define MRV indicators (with uncertainties quantified) (e.g., species/functional group biomass, geographic distribution, seasonal patterns, residence time assumptions). - develop alternative carbon accounting approaches to derive carbon credits - may operate as non-fungible assets requiring MRV approaches capable of capturing these ecosystem services. 	Climate ministries; statistical offices; universities; research institutes	2–4 years	GCF MRV support; FAO MRV programmes	IPCC Wetlands Supplement; FAO MRV guidance ; Balmford et al. (2023); Annasawmy et al. (2026); Ramah et al. (2026)
6. Sectoral Mainstreaming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate BCEs into MSP, fisheries, tourism, DRR - Apply mitigation hierarchy for coastal development - Ensure local peoples and small-scale food-producing communities are engaged - Apply blue carbon investments with sustainable livelihoods and equitable benefit-sharing across SWIO 	Planning ministries; fisheries authorities; tourism boards; district-level community associations	3–6 years	Development banks; resilience funds	Ocean Panel ; UNEP coastal planning guidance

Table 3. Phase 3 – Scaling, Finance & Regional Leadership (Years 5-15). CBD stands for Convention on Biological Diversity.

Action Area	Specific Actions	Lead / Supporting Institutions	Timeframe	Finance Options	Key References
7. Blue Carbon Finance Mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop national frameworks for carbon markets - Explore results-based finance, blue bonds, debt-for-nature swaps - Establish safeguards & benefit-sharing Mobile blue carbon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore blockchain-based tokenization frameworks - Pilot digital certification architectures (e.g., Orb-type platforms) - Develop mechanisms adapted to the scale of blue carbon abatement 	Finance ministries; central banks; Blue Economy units	5–10 years	Carbon markets; blue bonds; blended finance; Multilateral Development Banks; Blue Carbon Buyers Alliance; philanthropic/public finance actors; United Nations REDD program; GEF	Ocean Panel finance guidance; IUCN finance frameworks; Hilmi et al. (2023); Chami et al. (2019)
8. Regional Knowledge Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create SWIO blue carbon hub - Share datasets, emission factors, protocols - Joint training & peer review 	IOC; WIOMSA; African Union; regional universities; research institutes	5–10 years	Regional cooperation funds; European Union; SIDS programmes	WIOMSA regional BCE studies
9. Global Positioning & Diplomacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Showcase SWIO leadership in UNFCCC, Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction - Promote regional standards & south-south cooperation 	Foreign affairs; environment ministries	5–15 years	Climate diplomacy funds; partnerships	UNFCCC & CBD guidance on nature-based solutions

6. BLUE CARBON ROADMAP FOR IMPLEMENTATION IN THE SWIO

- Unlocking blue carbon potential in the SWIO requires a phased and coordinated approach that combines robust scientific baselines, enabling policy frameworks, and sustained long-term financing mechanisms (Table 1). Early action should focus on high resolution mapping, ground-truthing and assessment of mangrove and seagrass carbon stocks, data compilation and assessment of mobile blue carbon stocks, alongside strengthened institutional coordination, and signalling political commitment by integrating blue carbon solutions into NDCs under the Paris Agreement, which would be an important enabler for scaling existing initiatives. Building on this foundation, pilot projects and national MRV systems can support policy mainstreaming across coastal planning, fisheries, tourism, and disaster risk reduction sectors (e.g., linked to sea level rise and coastal protection) (Table 2). This phase should also advance scientific and policy recognition of mobile blue carbon. Over the longer term, scaling mobile blue carbon solutions will depend on the development of dedicated finance mechanisms, coordinated scientific research and regional capacity sharing for methodological development on mobile blue carbon solutions, and aligned diplomatic engagement, positioning the SWIO region as a world leader in nature-based climate solutions while delivering biodiversity and socio-economic benefits (Table 3).

- In parallel, implementation of the BBNJ Agreement presents an opportunity to extend blue carbon considerations into areas beyond national jurisdiction through the potential designation of high seas MPAs. Regional governance frameworks, including those operating under the Nairobi Convention, already provide an important platform for coordinated marine environmental management, scientific collaboration, and policy alignment across the Western Indian Ocean, which can support the integration and scaling of blue carbon initiatives.

7. REQUIRED MECHANISMS TO TRIGGER REGIONAL CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT IN BLUE CARBON ACCOUNTING

- Although not presently marketable, the rapidly growing interest in deep-sea blue carbon solutions will ultimately drive action in the science, finance, and governance fields to value these ecosystem services in the future (Zhong et al., 2023). Developing regional capacity to engage with this emerging agenda is therefore a strategic priority for the SWIO. The UAE Oceanic Blue Carbon Pilot Study, led by the Abu Dhabi Global Environmental Data Initiative, provides a useful model for the SWIO region. Rather than focusing on immediate market integration, the UAE initiative prioritised national-scale assessment, data integration, and the exploration of policy options for mobile blue carbon solutions (Lutz et al., 2019). This stepwise approach highlights how pilot studies can be used as capacity-development platforms—strengthening national expertise, identifying methodological gaps, and preparing institutions for future international accounting and finance mechanisms.

- Developing and assessing such approaches would require targeted capacity-sharing mechanisms, including: (i) specialised

training for regional scientists and practitioners in deep-ocean carbon processes and ecosystem service valuation; (ii) the establishment of interdisciplinary working groups linking marine science institutions, national statistical offices, and finance regulators; (iii) technical partnerships with organisations experienced in digital MRV systems, carbon registries, and environmental data infrastructures; and (iv) the development of national guidance and regulatory sandboxes to test innovative valuation approaches under controlled, non-market conditions. The Seychelles Seagrass Mapping and Carbon Assessment project provides a practical illustration of how such capacity can be built in a phased manner, serving as a pilot for the Large-scale Seagrass Mapping and Management Initiative, funded by PEW Charitable Trusts and supported regionally by the Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association (<https://www.lasmmi.org/>). Through coordinated data generation, regional training, and policy engagement, this initiative demonstrates how pilot projects can simultaneously strengthen scientific capacity, institutional coordination, and readiness for future blue carbon accounting—an approach that could be adapted and scaled to emerging deep-ocean and mobile blue carbon pathways.

- Effective capacity development in the SWIO should prioritise strengthening local scientific leadership while embedding mechanisms for regional capacity sharing. This includes supporting long-term career pathways for early- and mid-career researchers and enhancing access to oceanographic infrastructure and analytical tools. Capacity-development efforts are most effective when coupled with structured knowledge exchange among regional institutions, ensuring that expertise and lessons learned are retained within the region and contribute to a sustained, locally driven blue carbon research and governance agenda.

8. CONSIDERATIONS FOR LEGAL SYSTEM REFORMS

- The strong incentives to translate blue carbon into economic calculations as well as the trends for governance reforms discussed in international convention forums can no longer be overlooked. Logistical and legal frameworks should be established, to integrate blue carbon services into States' national accounting (e.g., national balance sheets) and investment payments for carbon credits. Once a carbon market for a specific carbon resource is established, States would have to implement legal frameworks to manage that carbon service, notably in EEZs and in the distant areas from the established baseline (according to geomorphology and to the international Law of the Sea provided by UNCLOS, the official baseline is more or less close to the coastline).

- In cases of joint management areas between the Republics of Mauritius and Seychelles, this discussion around joint management of carbon services of the underlying waters could become an additional area of cooperation between the two States, noting that cooperation is already organised under two bilateral legal modalities established since 2012 (JMA Treaty). In ABNJ adjacent to States, the issue also deserves attention through the identification of regional incentives and

legal mechanisms, alongside the establishment of regional scientific task forces for these difficult-to-access and assess areas (Galletti, 2026). An example of such regional incentives is provided by the WIO Regional Ocean Governance Strategy (WIO ROGS) dialogues (2022-2024) under the auspices of the Nairobi Convention (Galletti et al., 2024). The inclusion of a Regional Ocean Account as part of WIO ROGS was discussed, with blue carbon identified as a core element, along with a platform enabling an Ocean Account framework that could also facilitate sustainable investment. In the future, regional agreements to manage carbon services should further be developed, negotiated, and implemented. Blue carbon, as an innovative field of activity, is therefore likely to experience significant legal development.

- Currently, the scientific and financial steps aimed at making static blue carbon solutions profitable as an economic asset are the most often described. These approaches align with the concept of national marine heritage, whereby States hold natural capital within their marine and submarine limits of their national jurisdiction. This framing could extend to mobile blue carbon, as carbon sequestration services generated by mobile marine fauna within EEZ ecosystems contribute to national ocean natural capital, even when the organisms themselves move across jurisdictions. Legislation and regulation could be drafted to value this economic asset, ensuring that it is exploited by the holder State or exploited in ways that provide benefits to that State (e.g., in terms of public finances). Legal texts may also consider blue carbon as a resource to be conserved (i.e., not be consumed or destroyed) because it provides ecological services that cannot be replaced. These services are more varied than previously understood, and delivered to surrounding surfaces and ecosystems, or further afield, up to the wider western Indian Ocean (WIO) basin. This dimension may be reflected in references to WIO BCEs.
- A pivotal point is that blue carbon production sites should not be considered solely under economic or business law but should be fully addressed within existing and emerging environmental law. Environmental law at sea remains incomplete in many legislations. A clear direction moving forward is therefore to create or strengthen the protection of habitats and species that enable blue carbon services. Enacting protective instruments is one option to support public policies aimed at avoiding ecosystem destruction. Another direction is to develop forms of compensation capable of encouraging States not to destroy these ecosystems. Compensation, including payments to those who conserve ecosystems, is well established in the literature and gains particular relevance in the context of blue carbon, since the climate regulation services it provides often extend beyond the exclusive benefit of the coastal State to other regions or SIDS. Robust scientific research would help quantify and demonstrate these services using objective oceanic datasets (Ternon et al., 2026).
- Regardless of whether blue carbon is legally defined as an economic asset or as a natural heritage, the crucial issue remains its conservation. Conserving, and thus protecting, blue carbon capacities will require the regulation of human

activities (e.g., fishing, mining, dredging, maritime transport, and pollution) to prevent harm to the carbon service and to the physical and ecological areas from which the blue carbon originates. Any legal strategy for BCEs may therefore include definitions and measures enabling protection, restoration, and accountability for BCE loss, in a deterrent manner, so that these species and habitats are no longer disregarded.

9. CONCLUSION

As countries globally are ramping up their blue carbon projects and investing in marine carbon dioxide removal technologies to achieve net zero emissions, such as ocean afforestation, ocean fertilization, alkalinity enhancement, to name only a few, island states of the SWIO would stand to lose if they do not actively engage in the blue carbon scientific research and blue carbon valuation. Recognising and valuing both coastal and static, and deep-sea and mobile blue carbon solutions would allow Mauritius, Madagascar, and Seychelles to account for the climate services provided by their ocean territories. Doing so represents a unique opportunity to align conservation, climate action, and economic development in the SWIO. The work required to achieve market integration and approach the Holy Grail or assigned ideal of net zero emissions, is significant. This objective is unlikely to be attainable without incorporating blue carbon solutions into national accounting systems. National blue carbon accounting must therefore become more precise and nuanced, while remaining attentive to the potential risks associated with emerging technologies.

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